

African Swine Fever: A major threat to the swine industry

Deepika^{1*}, Pardeep², Pooja Gill³

^{1*}B.V.Sc. & A.H. interneer, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education & Research, Puducherry, 605009.

²B.V.Sc. & A.H. interneer, International Institute of Veterinary Education & Research, Rohtak, 124001.

³B.V.Sc. & A.H. interneer, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education & Research, Puducherry, 605009.

Abstract

African swine fever (ASF) is a devastating, non-zoonotic origin hemorrhagic fever of pigs with a 100% mortality rate. It causes major economic losses, threatens food security & limits the swine industry badly in affected areas. It is gaining more importance as it possesses wild hogs as their reservoirs presenting a major snag in its control. No effective vaccine has been developed against ASF virus, so the prevention is the most reliable strategy to combat this threat to swine industry.

Introduction

African swine fever is one of the most important of all swine diseases due to its significant sanitary and socioeconomic consequences. It is a highly contagious disease of pigs and wild boars causing 100% mortality (Patil *et al.*, 2020). It was first reported in east Africa in the early 1900s in domestic pigs and warthogs. OIE has listed ASF as a notifiable disease. The disease is reported to be non-zoonotic, but it is readily gets transmitted from one pig to another by direct contact. The mortality rate in the unexposed pigs varies from 0 to 100% depending on the virus, host, dose, and the route of exposure to the virus. It only affects porcine species, both wild and domestic, and produces a variety of clinical signs such as fever, and functional disorders such as the respiratory and digestive systems. Soft ticks of the genus *Ornithodoros* spp. act as biological vectors and reservoirs for the virus.

Etiology

African swine fever virus (ASFV) belongs to the genus *Asfivirus* of the family *Asfarviridae*. It is an enveloped virus containing linear double-stranded DNA possessing a genome size of 190 kbp. There are 24 distinct genotypes classified based on the p72 protein (Yoo *et al.*, 2020).

Epidemiology

Domestic pigs, warthogs, bushpigs, and giant forest hogs are the host of ASF. *Ornithodoros*

spp. ticks (Argasid ticks) serve as biological vectors and reservoir hosts for ASF. ASF is endemic in sub-Saharan Africa and the island of Sardinia, Italy. Transcontinental spread first occurred to Spain and Portugal in 1957 and 1960, respectively and from there to other countries in Europe, South America, and the Caribbean. In 2017, the ASF outbreak was reported in Russian area near its border with Mongolia (Central Asia). In August 2018, first outbreak of ASF was reported in China followed by several cases in other Asian countries. On May 21, 2020, OIE published the first report of ASF in two states of India (Assam & Arunachal Pradesh) reporting the mortality of a total of 3701 pigs. An outbreak has been reported in August 2022, in Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, & Punjab state.

Transmission

- Through the bites of soft ticks.
- Through inoculation with contaminated syringes and the use of contaminated surgical equipment.
- Through the introduction of infected pigs to the herd.

Clinical signs

ASF has an incubation period of 4-19 days.

- **Acute Form:** characterized by anorexia, ataxia, erythema & cyanotic blotching of the skin, vomiting, hemorrhagic diarrhea, and abortion in pregnant sows (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Cyanotic patches on the ears of ASF affected pig (Gil *et al.*, 2012)

- **Subacute form:** persistent or fluctuating fever lasts for up to 20 days.
- **Chronic form:** may persist for up to several months. Various clinical signs such as cutaneous ulcers, arthritis, emaciation, pneumonia, abortion, etc.

Diagnosis

- a) Based on the clinical signs and post-mortem lesions such as splenomegaly and visceral haemorrhages).
- b) Molecular techniques such as PCR.
- c) Serological assays such as ELISA, combined PCR- lateral flow strip (LFS) assay, indirect immunoperoxidase test & indirect immunofluorescence test is useful for detecting specific antibodies.

Prevention & Control

- Various education programs and campaigns have been held to stop people from carrying infectious materials to new areas.
- Implementing the ban on swill feeding to pigs or the proper heat treatment of swill to avoid the risk of ASF outbreak in naïve population.
- Strict border control is needed to block the introduction of contaminated meat items to naïve areas.
- Strict quarantine of the newly introduced animals to the existing flock.
- Special attention should be given to the management of animal transport, including disinfection of the vehicles.
- Proper disposal of the carcass by incineration.
- Separation of the domestic pigs from wild hogs by high fencing.
- No effective vaccine has been developed yet.

Conclusion

The swine industry is currently in flourishing stage in many states of India. It is a highly beneficial industry from the point of input & economic benefits but certain diseases such as CSF, ASF, etc. are major barriers to its further spread. African swine fever is a highly contagious & hemorrhagic viral disease of the swine which is responsible for the major economic loss to the industry. It is a highly fatal disease having no treatment or vaccine, thus, requires suitable hygienic & preventive measures to limit its spread.

References

- Patil, S. S., Suresh, K. P., Vashist, V., Prajapati, A., Pattnaik, B., & Roy, P. 2020. African swine fever: A permanent threat to Indian pigs. *Veterinary World*, **13**(10), 2275.
- Yoo, D., Kim, H., Lee, J. Y., & Yoo, H. S. 2020. African swine fever: Etiology, epidemiological status in Korea, and perspective on control. *Journal of Veterinary Science*, **21**(2), e38-e38.
- Dixon, L. K., Stahl, K., Jori, F., Vial, L., & Pfeiffer, D. U. 2020. African swine fever epidemiology and control. *Annual Review of Animal Biosciences*, **8**, 221-246.
- Blome, S., Franzke, K., & Beer, M. 2020. African swine fever—A review of current knowledge. *Virus*

research, **287**, 198099.

- Wang, Z., Yu, W., Xie, R., Yang, S., & Chen, A. 2021. A strip of lateral flow gene assay using gold nanoparticles for point-of-care diagnosis of African swine fever virus in limited environment. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, **413**(18), 4665-4672.
- Jurado, C., Martinez-Aviles, M., De La Torre, A., Štukelj, M., de Carvalho Ferreira, H. C., Cerioli, M., & Bellini, S. 2018. Relevant measures to prevent the spread of African swine fever in the European Union domestic pig sector. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, **5**, 77.

